

The Role of Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor in Diabetic Polyneuropathy

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ABSTRACT Diabetic polyneuropathy (DPN) is the most common microvascular complication in diabetes mellitus (DM). The nerve fibres injury was caused by the interaction between metabolic and vascular factor. Prolonged hyperglycemia will induce several mechanisms, such as sorbitol pathway, hypoxia, oxidative stress, and increased of advanced glycation end products (AGE). Those mechanisms will trigger the production of vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF). The production of VEGF in neovascularisation was followed by the changes in microvascular structure that were marked by the enhancement of arterial basal membrane, vein distention, arteriovenous shunting, intimal hyperplasia and hypertrophy, and endothelial fenestration. The VEGF production was a response to the hyperglycemia that was considered related to endotheliopathy and increased vascular permeability. Therefore, VEGF was acknowledged to contribute to hypoxia and acts as a potential proinflammatory substance. Nevertheless, VEGF also was considered to have a neuroprotective activity by its capability to trigger remyelination and neurogenesis. Based on this evidence, VEGF was assumed to have 2 different roles (dual effect) which are first by acting in the pathogenesis of DPN by induced hypoxia, increased vascular permeability, and caused inflammation, and second acts as a protective agent by induced nerve regeneration. This review is aimed to describe the proposed role of VEGF in the pathogenesis of DPN as well as some genetic studies regarding VEGF gene and its association with DPN.

KEYWORDS VEGF, vascular endothelial growth factor, diabetic polyneuropathy, DPN

Introduction

The microvascular complication is a general problem that can be found in diabetes mellitus (DM) patient. Approximately 72% of DM patient suffered one of the microvascular complications, retinopathy, nephropathy, and neuropathy. The main risk factors that contributed to increasing the microvascular complications are genetics, poor glycemic control, duration of DM, and hypertension. The other risk factors are cholesterol level, smoking,

and obesity [1].

Diabetic polyneuropathy (DPN) is a disorder involving the peripheral nervous system as the part of microvascular complications. The injury process of the nerve fibres as a result of DM can be divided into two main factors; (1) metabolic factor, and (2) vascular/ischemia factor. The metabolic factor underlying the length dependent polyneuropathy, whereas the ischemia factor and inflammation that occur simultaneously contribute to focal neuropathy [2].

Angiogenesis and neovascularisation mediate the metabolic and vascular factor. Hyperglycemia triggers several chemical processes that will produce substances that will harm the nerve fibres. One of those triggered chemical processes is the increase of vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) that will stimulate endothelial proliferation as an initial part in angiogenesis and neovascularisation process [3–5].

Based on these reasons, we are trying to describe the pro-

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posed role of VEGF in the pathogenesis of DPN as well as some genetic studies regarding VEGF gene and its association with DPN.

Pathogenesis of DPN

Hyperglycemia has a vital role in the occurrence and progressivity of DPN. Prolonged hyperglycemia in DM will change several mechanisms; (1) polyol pathway, (2) hexosamine pathway, (3) activation of protein kinase C (PKC), and (4) accumulation of advanced glycation end-products (AGE). Each process will end up damaging the nerve fibres by triggering the imbalance of mitochondrial redox reaction that will overproduce the reactive oxygen species (ROS). Furthermore, the increase of intracellular oxidative stress will stimulate the activation of poly (ADP-ribose) polymerase (PARP). These processes are involved in the alteration of the gene expression regulation that contributed to the inflammation process [6].

The alteration in the polyol pathway triggers the sorbitol accumulation and alteration of NAD/NADH ratio that will lower the neuronal blood flow, in the end, hypoxia and oxidative stress will occur. Moreover, the alteration in the polyol pathway will increase the production of fructose via sorbitol oxidation process. Formation of fructose will lower the NADPH level which will worsen the imbalance of redox reaction [6,7].

The production of fructose-6-phosphate assists the alteration in the hexosamine pathway as an excess product of glycolysis. This process will produce uridine diphosphate-n-acetyl glucosamine (UDP-GlcNAc), a molecule that can alter gene expression. Hyperglycemia state and the excess production of GlcNAc will increase the activation of Sp1 that responsible in the gene expression of transforming growth factor- β 1 (TGF- β 1) and plasminogen activator inhibitor-1 (PAI-1). Overexpression of TGF- β 1 will increase the production of the collagen matrix and thereby increase endothelial fibrosis and lower the proliferation of capillary mesangial cells. In the meantime, the overexpression of PAI-1 will trigger the mitosis of vascular smooth muscle cells that involve in atherosclerosis.

Overexpression of PAI-1 is triggered by the activation of protein kinase C (PKC) pathway that stimulates vasoconstriction and finally results in lowering the neuronal blood flow. The increased production of PKC- β will also trigger the overexpression of angiogenic VEGF protein, PAI-1, natural factor-kappa B (NF - kB), and TGF- β , all of which involved in the microvascular complication of DM such as, retinopathy, nephropathy, and cardiovascular event, and also neuropathy [4,6].

The hyperglycemic state will increase the diacylglycerol and influence Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase enzyme and also other proteins that useful in maintaining membrane potential and nerve conduction velocity. Glucose autoxidation in the hyperglycemic state will increase the production of ROS and AGE. Furthermore, AGE will bind to the surface cell receptor that activates the nuclear factor kappa-light-chain-enhancer of activated B cells that result in endothelial dysfunction and lowered neuronal blood flow. Diabetes mellitus will also disrupt the production of gamma linoleic acid that lower the synthesis of vasoactive prostanoid in microvascular vessels. This disturbance will lower the neuronal blood flow and cause hypoxia. Hypoxia state that is triggered by these processes is believed as the primary neuronal damage in diabetic neuropathy. In the damaged cells, the level of nerve growth factor (NGF), brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF), and neurotrophin 4/5 is decline which is essential in maintaining the integrity of axons [2,3].

Poly (ADP-ribose) polymerase (PARP) was found in Schwann cell, endothelial cells, and a sensory neuron that is contributed in glucotoxicity. Poly (ADP-ribose) polymerase (PARP) will divide nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide (NAD⁺) into nicotinamide and ADP-ribose residue that is attached to nuclear protein. The results of this process are decreased in NAD⁺ level, alteration in gene expression and transcription, an increase of free radical, and facilitation of the PKC pathway and formation of AGE. Abnormalities that was triggered by this process are a reduction of nerve conduction velocity, neuropathy of small nerve fibres, neurovascular abnormalities, retinopathy, thermal and mechanical hyperalgesia, and tactile allodynia [6,8].

Prolonged hyperglycemia stimulates oxidative stress in DM. The oxidative stress occurred by the imbalance of ROS, and antioxidant compounds such as superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase, glutathione, vitamin C or E. Included in ROS are superoxide anion, hydroxyl radical, peroxynitrite, and hydrogen peroxide. Ischemia/vascular factor is mainly shown by the thickening and hyalinization of the small vessel wall along with the reduplication of basal lamina around the endothelium. This process is known as microangiopathy, similar to the other complication process in DM engaging the eyes, kidneys, and heart. Thickening of the small vessel wall occurs simultaneously with the decrease or damaged of intraepidermal small fibre. If this process continues, the degeneration of nerve fibres in dying back phenomenon and Wallerian degeneration will occur, resulting in clinical symptoms that begin in pain then tingling and the interruption of other prominent nerve fibres [9,10].

Endothelial dysfunction plays a vital role in initiating the cellular process that will progress to microvascular complication in DM. Decreased of nitric oxide (NO) and increased of endothelin-1 will trigger the endothelial dysfunction. Furthermore, this process will improve the vascular tone that magnifies the microvascular damage. Thickening of basal membrane, pericyte degeneration, and microvascular hyperplasia of endoneurial are the pathologic changes that generally found in vascular damaged, whereas, in nerve fibres damaged, broken of fibres and myelin even degeneration can be seen. Alteration in functional structure of nerves and blood vessels as a result of chronic hyperglycemia is occurred simultaneously [11]

VEGF

Vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) is a critical proangiogenic substance in the human body. The VEGF also potentiates the vascular hypermeability, a general phenomenon along with the angiogenesis process. Derivatives of VEGF including VEGF-A, VEGF-B, VEGF-C, VEGF-D and two similar compounds of VEGF coded by parapoxvirus (VEGF-E and VEGF-F), and placenta growth factor (PlGF) that also involved in the tissue of myocardium, lungs, spleen, and liver. Each VEGF derivative is functionally and structurally a different substance that coded by a different gene. The VEGF-B is mainly expressed by the mature myocardium, skeletal muscle, and pancreas. The VEGF-C is primarily involved in angiogenesis of lymphatic system. The VEGF-D is generally involved in the formation of embryonic lung tissue and found in very high level in lung tissue. The VEGF E and F are considered involved in the reaction to the virus-infected cells. Placenta growth factor (PlGF) is involved in the menstrual cycle and placenta in women. The VEGF-A (mainly) and B need to bind with heparan sulfate proteoglycan to be able to enter and solve in plasma. This binding function as a storage form of VEGF and increase the binding potential to

receptors [12].

Angiogenesis and vascular permeability mainly mediated by VEGF-A, often mention as VEGF, found circulating in plasma and involved in several vascular diseases that recently attracted much attention of researchers [13]. Vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF) is a mitogen substance in endothelial cells. It is also known as vasopermeabel and vasculotrophin factor which is a homodimer glycoprotein, about 45-kDa. Expression of VEGF is increased in hypoxia state [14,15].

The VEGF is also found in an artery, vein, and lymph vessels. The VEGF is considered as an essential factor that supports the endothelial survival. The VEGF can trigger the expression of anti-apoptosis protein Bcl-21 and A1 in human endothelium. Mitogenic effect of VEGF in endothelial is not only occurred in high vascularity organ, but also in pancreas cells, Schwann cells, and retinal pigment cells. Besides function as a mitogen, VEGF also involved in increasing the vascular permeability. This understanding is based on the increase of protein extravasation in guinea pig mice skin tissue presented by VEGF. Increased vascular permeability is a key in angiogenesis. It also occurred as the VEGF stimulate the fenestrated endothelial changes [13].

There are several receptors contributed to VEGF function, VEGFR-1 (Flt-1) and VEGFR-2 (Flt-1/KDR) both of which are tyrosine kinase (TK) receptors. The binding response of VEGF-Flt-1 and VEGF-KDR are different. If VEGF bind to KDR, there will be an induction of mitogenesis and chemotaxis and an increased in vascular permeability. If VEGF bind to Flt-1, stimulation of tyrosine phosphorylase on endothelial cells will be initiated, resulting in the formation of platelet-activating factor (PAF). This process will trigger mitosis and migration, and increase the vascular permeability. The PAF has many activities after being initiated, one of the most important is to trigger the accumulation and adhesion of inflammation cells encouraging the expression of a potent angiogenic factor and chemokine-like acid fibroblast factor, fundamental fibroblast growth factors, and macrophage inflammatory protein 2 [13].

The affinity of VEGF-A to VEGFR-1 is higher than VEGFR-2, but the binding of VEGF to VEGFR-1 will initiate the weaker mitogenesis process than the binding of VEGF to VEGFR-2. The VEGFR-1 also potentiates the pathologic vascularisation and suppresses the angiogenesis that is triggered by VEGFR-2, besides it will induce the migration of mononuclear phagocyte cells to cross the endothelium. Whereas, activated VEGFR-2 involved in intracellular signal transduction as a response to VEGF binding [12–14,16]. The binding of VEGF and VEGFR-2 mainly forms the proangiogenic signal. This binding will activate the PLC γ -PKC-MAPK, the primary signal of proliferated endothelium. Expression of VEGFR-1 by the derivatives cells of macrophage facilitate the migration of those cells. Nervous systems also express both of VEGFR [17].

VEGF in DPN

The VEGF can increase the microvascular permeability thus allow it to be crossed by macromolecules. The increased permeability can be observed in a tumour, injured tissue, or chronic inflammation. Besides, VEGF also forms fenestration on endothelial and disorganise endothelial protein, such as VE-cadherin and occludin. Evidence showed that in mesenteric cells, the effect of increased vascular permeability was mediated by the binding of VEGF to VEGFR-2, then activates the PLC. This result will increase diacylglycerol production and calcium influx. The binding of VEGF and VEGFR-1 is also increased as the effect of

increased microvascular permeability. VEGF-A also induces nitric Oxide (NO), this endogenous NA is believed has an essential role in the increased vascular permeability [18].

The VEGF is known as a proinflammatory cytokine by increasing the vascular permeability, triggers endothelial molecule adhesion by acting as chemoattractant monocyte. It was strongly expressed in keratinocyte and psoriasis wound where the increased vascular permeability and angiogenesis commonly found [18]. Oztruk et al. (2009) [19] described VEGF and monocyte chemoattractant protein (MCP-1) is increased in diabetic retinopathy. They concluded that the increased VEGF and MCP-1 are considered to involve in the pathologic process of complicated DM such as diabetic retinopathy. In the nervous system, VEGF induced Schwann cells proliferation, trigger axonal growth, and increase the survival of neuron and Schwann cells. It also triggers the migration of Schwann cells and induces the damaged nerve fibres [20]. Even so, in vascular level, the increased of VEGF will induce the endothelial proliferation but also thicken the vascular wall and caused obstruction. This event will worsen the hypoxia in the target tissue. If this even takes place in nerve blood vessel, it will worsen the neuronal hypoxia [21].

Expression and production of VEGF will increase in hypoxia state by hypoxia-inducible factor-1 (HIF-1), hyperglycemia, oxidative stress, and AGE which happen in DM followed by its microvascular complications [22,23].

According to Motawi et al. (2015) [24], the role of VEGF in polyneuropathy was mediated by the alteration of circulated angiogenic and antiangiogenic factor. Hyperglycemia will increase the production of VEGF by activating the sorbitol pathway, induce hypoxia state, and anaerobic intracellular metabolism, and increase the production of AGE. The increased VEGF will evoke neovascularisation, the general condition that commonly found in microvascular complication including polyneuropathy. The effects of VEGF on neuronal tissue are not understood entirely, although the protective effect starts to gain attention. The direct neurotrophic effect of VEGF to nerve fibres is still not known yet. It was believed that all neuronal effects happen as a result of increased VEGF, starting with angiogenesis and neovascularization in nerve blood vessel.

The structural abnormality in epineural blood vessels comprised of arterial basal membrane enhancement, vein distention, arteriovenous shunting, and neovascularization with minimal hyperplasia and hypertrophy of intima, followed by denervation. Neovascularization seemingly changes the normal structure of nerve blood vessel with hyalin thickening, endothelial hypertrophy, thickening and hyperplasia of basal membrane and lost of pericyte. The paradox is that the increase of nerve fibres neovascularisation in the early stage of DM, but systematically, there is ischemia as a disturbance of neovascularisation occurred. Furthermore, the oxidative stress will alter the structure and function of endothelial, resulting in microcirculation defect by peroxidation of the lipid membrane, protein, and DNA. Upregulation of (reticular activating system) RAS and increased endothelin-1 will lower neuronal blood flow. We can conclude that the augmentation of angiogenesis and oxidative stress is simultaneous and it contributed to neuronal damage [25].

Doupis et al. (2009) [26] discovered that hyperglycemia, oxidative stress, and AGE formation trigger the release of VEGF in DM. The level of VEGF is higher in a study group with DPN, and diabetic neuropathic pain compares to the control group. Along with it, the inflammatory cytokines level like RANTES,

CRP, TNF- α , sICAM, sVCAM, fibrinogen, leptin, increases significantly in the study group. It proved the dysfunction of inflamed endothelium in a combination aspect of vascular and metabolic plays a vital role in the pathogenesis of DPN. Other than involved in angiogenesis and endothelial dysfunction, VEGF also involved in other inflammatory cytokines in the pathogenesis process [27].

The increased level of VEGF in the early phase of DPN can act as a response to hypoxia and oxidative stress in targeted endothelium. Meanwhile, ischemic respond to nerve fibres will trigger the increase of VEGF expression in an attempt to protect the nerve and maintain axonally or myelin integrity. This phenomenon is called the dual effect of VEGF [22]. The VEGF will increase the vascular permeability and thicken the basal membrane thus worsen the nerve fibres damage, simultaneously, when VEGF exposed to nerve fibres, it will act as a protective factor. Via VEGFR-2, it double acts as neuroprotective agent. Along with other angioneurins, like IGF-1, TGF- β 1, EPO, FGF2, HGF, EGF, and PGRN angioneurins were believed to have a positive effect on remyelination and neurogenesis [28].

Genetic Study of VEGF in DPN

Several studies have discovered the role of VEGF gene variants in DPN. The polymorphism of VEGF gene in the position 7 C/T, 936 C/T, 1001 G/C, 1154 G/A, dan 2578 C/A location has been investigated in subjects with DPN [21,29,30]. In those variants, polymorphism of VEGF gene 7 C/T and 936 C/T were associated with DPN. According to Kim et al. (2009) and Zhang et al. (2014) [21,29], the polymorphism of VEGF gene 936 C/T (rs3025039) was also related with VEGF level. Zhang et al. (2014) [21] found that the polymorphism of VEGF gene 936 C/T 3'UTR was associated with DPN. The CC genotype in that location associated with an increased risk for DPN. Moreover, VEGF serum in CC genotype was significantly higher compared to other genotypes.

Kim et al. (2009) [29] previously emphasized the role of VEGF 936 C/T gene polymorphism in the event of diabetic microvascular complications in Korea. This study was not able to find the relation of polymorphism gene in the diabetic neuropathy or nephropathy. Nevertheless, this study confirmed that the VEGF 936 C/T gene polymorphism was related to VEGF plasma. In this study T allele and TT genotype were associated with higher VEGF level compared to other allele and genotype. The basic mechanism of correlation between VEGF 936 C/T gene polymorphism was not known entirely. One possible explanation is that VEGF 936 C/T gene polymorphism probably interacts with other SNP form of VEGF gene that is not known yet and acts together in transcription. The mRNA analysis in VEGF 936 C/T gene mutation product showed no changes that can explain the increase and decrease of VEGF plasma. The polymorphism of VEGF gene 936 C/T probably caused the loss of the binding site to AP-4 factor, a transcription factor in a helix-loop-helix form that is important in VEGF expression [31].

Conclusion

The starting point of these several neuronal damage processes in DM was hyperglycemia as other microvascular complications. Hyperglycemia triggers some series of processes, specifically increase of sorbitol, PKC, DAG, and AGE, within which trigger the ROS and oxidative stress formation along with the increased proinflammatory cytokine expression. These processes also in-

creased the production and expression of VEGF, resulting in angiogenesis, endotheliopathy, and increased vascular membrane permeability. The VEGF acts in DPN pathogenesis through this process. Nevertheless, VEGF also has a neuroprotective characteristic as it can trigger remyelination and neurogenesis.

Competing Interests

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None

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